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A REVIEW: COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

In the branch of medicine the oral route stands as the foremost preference for drug administration, particularly when aiming for systemic effects. However, the oral route proves inadequate for delivering intended to treat lower gastrointestinal diseases as they often encounter premature release within the upper gastrointestinal tract, there has been a comprehensive and extensive analysis of colon-specific drug delivery system over the past two decades. These specialized are designed to precisely target drugs to specific sites within the colon, there by augmenting the therapeutic impact of the absorbed in contemporary medical practice, drugs are increasingly directed towards the colon via the rectal route in the recent years, has gained prominence as a means to precisely target drug delivery to colon enabling the potential for both localized and systemic drug effects in local drug delivery system we can treat bowel disease such as ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease, Amoebiosis, colonic cancer. To achieve effective colon-targeted drug delivery, it is necessary to safeguard the drug from degradation, premature release, and absorption in the upper gastrointestinal tract and ensure precise control of its release while protecting it from degradation in the colon. This review is focused on the introduction of colon anatomy of colon micro flora and Its importance, applications of colon drug delivery system, new opportunities of colon drug delivery system, evaluation of colon drug delivery system and drug performance of anticancer drugs by colon drug delivery system.

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INTRODUCTION

Colon targeted drug delivery systems is a unique operation to deliver medications precisely to the lower gastrointestinal tract with a primary focus on the colon. Their significance become evident when considering the need to protect drugs from degradation in the small intestine due to enzymatic secretions, making them particularly well-suited for treating colonic disease such as colon cancer, ulcerative colitis, and Crohn's disease.

The concept of colon targeted drug delivery found its origin in the pioneering work of Takaya. He developed pressure controlled colon delivery capsules using ethyl cellulose, a water insoluble substance. These capsules represent a significant leap forward in ensuring drug delivery to the colon. Further more, these systems employ PH dependent polymers including cellulose acetate phthalates (CAP), hydroxypropyl methylcellulose phthalate (HPMC) 50 and 55, as well as copolymers like Eudragit 100 and Eudragit L, underscoring their evolution over the past few decades.

In a world where the prevalence of colonic diseases especially colon cancer, has surged globally, there is a pressing need for effective treatments. The sharp reality of more than 1.9 Million new cases of colorectal cancer and over 930,000 deaths attribute to it in 2020 places colon cancer as the second leading cause of cancer related mortality worldwide, additionally, the incidence of inflammatory bowel disease particularly in India is on a worrying rise.

They not only excel in localized disease treatment but also hold promise for systemic delivery of therapeutic proteins and peptides that are typically administered through injections. When taken orally these systems act as guards, protecting peptide drugs from degradation in the duodenum and jejunum, ultimately releasing them. The primary aim of a targeted drug delivery system is to achieve the desired drug concentration in the body. This is particularly crucial for drugs characterized by instability, poor solubility, a short half-life, a high volume of distribution or low absorption rates. Due to the colon's exceptional water absorption capacity. Adding another layer of complexity is the role played by colon bacteria resident microbes like Bacteroides, Bifidobacterium, Eubacterium, Peptococcus, Lactobacillus, and Clostridium. An array of reductive and hydrolytic enzymes, encompassing β -glucuronidase, β -galactosidase, albinosidase, and nitroreductase which contribute significantly to the breakdown of di, tri, and polysaccharides.

In summary, colon-targeted drug delivery systems represent a multifaceted approach that combines innovation with precision, offering a beacon of hope for the treatment of colonic diseases and holding the potential to revolutionize drug delivery on multiple fronts.

ADVANTAGES:

- Colon drug delivery used in the treatment of nicotine addiction
- Useful for delivery of proteins, peptides, which are being delivered by injections.
- Used in direct treatment of disease at that site, low dosing.
- The metabolism process like azoreduction and enzymatic cleavage takes place in colon which is responsible for the metabolism of many drugs and peptides like insulin.

DISADVANTAGES:

- Development of colon specific drug is difficult due to many biological barriers.
- Cytochrome (P450) class of drug metabolizing enzymes has lower affinity in the colonic mucosa.
- Single unit colon target drug delivery system has the disadvantage of unintentional disintegration of the formulation due to manufacturing deficiency of the formulation due to manufacturing deficiency or unusual gastric physiology.

NEED OF COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM:

- Targeted drug delivery into the colon helpful in treatment of diseases at that site, fewer systemic side effects and dose can be minimized.
- Serious diseases of the colon are treated more effectively if drugs were targeted to the colon. Example: Colonic cancers like colorectal cancer.
- The colon is a site where both local or systemic drug delivery could be achieved, topical treatment of inflammatory bowel disease, e.g. ulcerative colitis or Crohn's disease. Such inflammatory conditions are usually treated with glucocorticoids and sulphasalazine (targeted).

LIMITATIONS:

- For better delivery it should be in solution form before it arrives in the colon.
- fluid content in the colon is much lower and it is more viscous than in the upper part of gastro intestinal tract, through which dosage form has to traore reaching target site.
- The resident microflora could also affect colonic performance via metabolic degradation of the drug
- Lower surface area and relative tightness also affects the bioavailability of drugs.

PARTS OF COLON:

The colon has four parts which have the same structure and functions

1. ASCENDING COLON

This passes upwards from the caecum to the level of the Liver where it curves acutely to the left at the hepatic flexure to become the Transverse colon.

2. TRANSVERSE COLON

This part extends across the abdominal cavity in front of the duodenum and the stomach to the area of the duodenum and the stomach to the area of the spleen where it forms the splenic flexure and curves acutely downwards to become the descending colon.

3. DESENDING COLON

This passes down the left side the abdominal cavity then curves towards the midline at the level of the iliac crest it is known as the sigmoid colon.

4. SIGMOID COLON

This part describes an s-shaped curve in the pelvic cavity that continues downwards to become the rectum.

FUNCTIONS OF COLON

- The consolidation of the intestinal contents into feces by the absorption of the water and electrolytes and storage of feces until excreted from the body.
- To provide a favorable environment for the growth of colonic microorganisms.
- Absorption of H_2O and Na^+ from the lumen, and secretion of k^+ and HCO

COLONIC MICROFLORA

The human alimentary canal is highly populated with bacteria and other microflora at both ends of oral cavity and the colon/rectum. A healthy normal microflora is the first line of defense to invading pathogens and thus it is extremely important for the ability to fight off infections with enteric pathogens, furthermore it is necessary for a well functioning and effective digestion of nutrients resulting in good gut performance.

These are some foods which destroys gut Flora. so you should avoid these if you want to significantly improve your gastrointestinal health.

1. Red meat
2. Processed foods (pizza, burger)
3. Artificial sweeteners
4. Refined grains (maida)
5. Too much saturated fatty acids
6. Fried foods
7. Refined sugars
8. Ajinomoto (monosodium glutamate) commonly known as tasty salt.

TYPES OR MODIFIED RELEASE FORMULATIONS FOR COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS :

These are of two types

- Single unit colon targeted drug delivery system:
- Multiparticulate dosage form systems:

POLYMERS:

Polymers are the heart of pharmaceutical formulations either in conventional and novel drug delivery system. The drug release is sustaining, extending, modifying, controlling and targeted based on the use of polymer in different dosage forms and drug delivery system.

- Natural polymers
- Synthetic polymers

FACTORS AFFECTING CDDS:

Various factors that affect the CTDDS and decrease the bioavailability of the formulation.

1. Physiological factor
2. Pharmaceutical factor

1. PHYSIOLOGICAL FACTORS

➤ GASTROINTESTINAL TRANSIT

Gastrointestinal motility in fasted state proceeds through 4 phase over a period of 2-3 hours. The feeding state affects the normal pattern by irregular contractile activity.

➤ INTESTINE TRANSIT:

Small intestinal transit is not influenced by the physical state, size of the dosage form and the presence of food in the stomach. The mean transit time of the dosage form is about 3-4 hours to reach the ileocecal junction and the time period is consistent.

➤ COLONIC TRANSIT:

The bioavailability of drugs released from the dosage forms can be highly influenced by the colonic transit time. Small particles and solutions pass slowly through the proximal colon and in human being, Men shows shorter colonic transit time than women. The colonic transit time of capsule in adults is 20-35 hours, the transit time of capsule is independent of the capsule density

➤ GASTRIC EMPYTING:

Gastric emptying is fastest and most consistent. Emptying completes from 5-10 min up to 2 hrs, depending on phase of stomach at the time of drug administration. Gastric emptying can be considerably slowed by fed state.

➤ STOMACH AND INTESTINAL PH

Release and absorption of orally administered drugs are influenced by the gastro intestinal pH.

➤ COLONIC MICROFLORA AND ENZYMES:

The human alimentary canal is highly populated with bacteria and other microflora at both ends, are oral cavity and the colon/rectum. Other enzymes are glycosidase and glucuronidases produced by lactobacilli, bacteroids and bifidobacteria. The activity of enzyme is associated with the concentration of bacteria in particular region.

➤ COLONIC ABSORPTION:

The surface area of colon is much less compared to small intestine, and hence not ideally suited for absorption. Resident time of colon is 10-24 hours. Absorption is influenced by the transport of water, electrolytes and ammonia across the mucosa and it is more in the proximal colon and distal colon

MECHANISMS OF ABSORPTIONS

- Passing through colonocytes (transcellular transport)
- Passing between adjacent colonocytes (paracellular transport)

➤ COLONIC ABSORPTION OF MACROMOLECULES:

The absorption property of Bovine serum albumin is 0.13% from colon and 1.7% through small intestine. This is due to surface area difference.

➤ GASTRO INTESTINAL DISEASED STATE:

Crohn's disease, constipation, diarrhea and gastroenteritis may affect the release and absorption properties of colon specific drug delivery systems.

2. PHARMACEUTICAL FACTORS:

➤ DRUG CANDIDATE:

Drugs which show poor absorption from the stomach or intestine including peptide drugs are most suitable for colon specific drug delivery systems. Sulphasalazine and 5-ASA are widely used drugs for treatment of IBD and other diseases.

➤ DRUG CARRIER:

Drug carrier is very important factor to design CTDDS. For Selection of drug carrier firstly know about the type of drug and type of disease. According to drug and disease select the carrier. Carrier selection are affected by numerous factors such as :

- Chemical nature of drug
- Stability of drug
- Partition coefficient of drug

APPROACHES TO COLON-SPECIFIC DRUG DELIVERY:

Colon-specific drug delivery is considered beneficial in the treatment of colon-related diseases and the oral delivery of protein and peptide drugs. Generally, each colon-specific drug delivery system has been designed based on one of the following mechanisms with varying degrees of success

1. Coating with pH dependent polymers
 2. Coating with pH independent biodegradable polymers
 3. Microbially triggered drug delivery to the colon
- Prodrugs for drug delivery to colon
 - Hydrogels
 - Polysaccharide based approach for drug delivery to the colon

Formulations for colonic delivery are also suitable for delivery of drugs which are polar and susceptible to chemical and enzymatic degradation in the upper GI tract, in particular, therapeutic proteins and peptides. Proteins and peptides such as insulin, calcitonin and vasopressin may be delivered systemically via colonic absorption. Other examples include novel peptides such as cytokine inhibitors and antibiotics, which are useful in the treatment of inflammatory bowel diseases and GI infections, respectively. Apart from protecting these labile molecules, colon also offers an opportunistic site for oral delivery of vaccines. Because it is rich in lymphoid tissue. Therefore, the uptake of antigens through the colonic mucosa may lead to rapid and local production of antibodies. There is also an increasing interest in the colonic delivery for improving the oral bioavailability of drugs that are substrates of metabolizing enzymes is comparatively lower in the colonic mucosa than in the small intestine. Increasing bioavailability via a colonic formulation approach has also been found to be effective in minimizing unwanted side-effects. Drug release from this system is triggered by colonic microflora coupled with pH sensitive polymer coatings

GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS FOR DESIGN OF COLONIC FORMULATIONS

Formulations for colonic delivery are in general delayed-released dosage forms which may be designed either to provide a burst release or a sustained/ prolonged/ targeted.

- a. Pathology and of disease, especially the affected parts of the lower gastro intestinal tract.
- b. Physicochemical and biopharmaceutical properties of the drug such as solubility, stability and permeability at the intended site of delivery.
- c. The preferred release data of the drug.

The pH gradient of the GI tract is a very frequent physiological aspect taken into account while designing delayed release colonic formulations. There is an in normally healthy subjects gradual rise in luminal pH following the cecum (pH is 6.40.4), a drop in the duodenum (pH is 6.60.5) until the end of the ileum (pH is 7.50.4), and then a gradual rise from the Right to left colon, with a 7.0 ultimate value 0.7. Several publications claimed that modifications in stomach acid levels can be found in Inflammatory bowel disease patients, which should be taken into account when creating formulations with delayed release.

DIFFERENT APPROACHES FOR COLON TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM :

➤ MINI TABLETS APPROACH

In the approach unchanged release of the drugs and a very good patient compliance. In this mini-tablets approaches different techniques are used for the formulation such as core mini tablet filled with pulsincap in this technique polymers are used that release the drug in time depended manner and other techniques are capsule filled with matrix mini tablet in this technique use PH dependent and microsomal enzyme-dependent polymers.

➤ MICROSPHERES

A microsphere's practical size is 5200 nm. Microspheres with several advantages over an oral drug delivery system, including free-flowing characteristics. Microspheres are utilized treating local diseases, enhancing the stability of delicate medications, and for prolonged drug release. The matrix method is helpful for preparation of microspheres, such as polysaccharide-based microspheres. Combining prescription drugs treatment for amebiasis using a multi-particulate method and pectin metronidazole synthesis microsphere. A microemulsion containing nanoparticles of 5-ASA silicon dioxide for ulcerative colitis because they are highly effective and have little cytotoxicity.

➤ MUCOADHESIVE APPROACH

Microspheres and nanocarriers have been created for CTDDS. For instance, sodium alginate was utilized to make the Valdecoxib mucoadhesive matrix and the polymer was employed to coat the Eudragit S 100. Nano- and micro-carriers are formed for anti-inflammatory medications. Prepare the sodium naproxen. For the treatment of colitis, sodium alginate and Eudragit S100 polymer are used to create a mucoadhesive. produced NPs with improved mucoadhesive characteristics to extend the resistance duration of medication and its bioavailability. Making the oxaliplatin with gelatin suspension of hydrogel for colon cancer.

➤ CODESTEM

Codestem is a new CTDDS technology, this technology is used for overcome the problem related with pH dependent systems CODESTM is mixed method of pH dependent and microbially triggered CTDDS.

➤ MULTI-MATRIX SYSTEM

This system has been useful for the one dose therapy for improve patient compliance and efficacy of therapy. For example, prepare the multi-matrix system of mesalamine as a single dose for the treatment of the local diseases such as ulcerative colitis and inflammatory bowel disease. Time-dependent delivery system was useful for the delivery of the insulin to colon. For the long-term stability chrono topic system.

➤ PRESSURE CONTROLLED SYSTEM

The colon has higher pressures than the small intestine because of the effects of peristalsis. Drug administration capsules for the colon that are controlled under pressure are made of insoluble polymers like ethyl cellulose. The large intestine's luminal pressure is caused by peristaltic action, which is Because of the large intestine's contents, peristaltic motion raises its pressure more than small intestinal motion does. Due to the reabsorption of water, are more viscous. Various studies for CTDDS have been developed using Colonic luminal pressure, The capsule containing the medicine is used to create the pressure-controlled drug delivery mechanism.

➤ CARBON NANOTUBE

Single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs) made of paclitaxel are formed in carbon nanotubes. This consists of single-walled polyethylated nanotubes that have a high suppressive activity on tumors and paclitaxel, which is insoluble in water. As a result, it is making normal cells less poisonous and making them more water-soluble. The most commonly over expressed receptor for epidermal growth factor is seen in colon cancer. Using SWNT is ensuring chemotherapy medications. It is a new approach used for colon cancer it is very effective and useful based on the study of the discussion in the different international journal.

➤ NANOPARTICLES

Nano particles are a new class of medication delivery mechanism. The medication is directed to the colon using this technique. Carbon nanotubes and metallic nano particles are two different forms of NPs. NPs have a special quality, and the medical business uses this technique as a result. For instance, doxorubicin nanoparticles can be made using the pH-sensitive polymer polyacrylic acid to boost the drug's effectiveness and safety while also increasing its bioavailability. To make 5-fluorouracil nanoparticles for the mesosphere, medication that has been coated in guar gum to improve the drug's release when there are enzymes present.

METAL NONOPARTICLES

Metal nanoparticles are produced using reductive technology; they are primarily colloidal systems. Utilizing seed-based technology, synthesizing a few metal nanoparticles, like silica with pores. The colloidal suspensions are more contactable with the outside world when the liquid carrier is magnetized. This fluidity and magnetic fields have medical applications. In the present work, nickel oxide nanoparticles between 20 and 25nm are created, their cytotoxicity is investigated, and the results demonstrate decreased cytotoxicity. However, most metallic NPs are building up in the body and being classified as toxic.

MAGNETIC NANOPARTICLES

Magnetic nanoparticles produce magnetic fluctuation (alternating magnetic field), which produces the heating power that is utilized to treat cancer and tumors. Recent research using magnetic nanoparticles reveals that the MSR-1 strain of magneto tactic bacteria is the source of the natural manufacture *Gryphiswaldense magneto spirillum*. It is helpful for colon cancer's antineoplastic action. Due to its low effectiveness, thermotherapy is also employed for a number of tumors. By using this method to increase the intra-tumoral delivery of magnetic nanoparticles.

➤ OSMOTICALLY CONTROLLED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Osmotic units are the foundation of an osmotically regulated drug delivery system. The osmotic unit is a crucial component of this system. The osmotic units can be employed as one or five to six push-pull units. An example of a system controlled by osmotic pressure is the OROS-CT. This technique is employed for both systemic drug absorption and localized drug delivery to the colon. The osmotic unit has a diameter of 4 mm and consists of one osmotic unit. contained inside a thick gelatin capsule, Drug layer and osmotic push layer are a semi permeable membrane surrounds both units of the bilayer push-pull unit.

Osmotic push-pull unit. The medication is pushed and swollen by the created osmotic pressure, which transforms the drug into a flowable gel in the medication storage area. The medication gel is forced to flow through the swollen osmotic push-pull compartment by the semi permeable membrane and orifice are useful for controlling the water rate.

EVALUATION PARAMETES

1. IN VITRO DISSOLUTION TEST

The dissolving investigation makes use of the traditional basket approach. For the dissolving investigation, various buffers, including pH 6.8 and 7.4 phosphate buffer, are used. Investigate the drug's release at various pH levels. CTDDS dissolution testing is done using a variety of mediums. This approach is helpful for researching medication release.

2. IN-VITRO ENZYMIC TEST

Two assays are offered by in-vitro enzymatic testing. After creating a favorable environment for bacteria, the carrier drug system is incubated in a fermenter. Calculated drug release amounts at various time intervals. The research of drug release requires buffer media, which contains the rat dextranase and pectinase enzymes. "guineapig" The degradation of the polymer carrier has an impact on how much medication is released over time.

3. IN-VIVO EVALUATION TEST

Dogs, guinea pigs, rats, and other animals are utilized in in-vivo studies for CTDDS. Because the human GIT's anatomy and flora resemble those of dogs, guinea pigs, and rats. The rat, dog, and guinea pig GITs share the same environment as the human GIT.

4. GAMMA SCINTIGRAPHY

This technique is employed to study how quickly drugs move through the GIT. This technique is used to calculate the passage time. Because pharmacokinetic studies use scintigraphy, the locations of drug absorption are identified in these research. The gamma radiations from the individual are detected by a crystal. They offer the electronic output that is produced when energy is converted to light scintillation and amplified. This method uses minimal radiation are employed in patients, and they are noninvasive. Gamma scintigraphy is also effective for researching medication clearance and feeding the GIT. This method is useful for comprehending how drugs are delivered.

5. HIGH FREQUENCY CAPSULES

This approach is crucial for researching how well a medicine absorbs in the colon. This technique is employed to examine the drug's bioavailability in the colonic location. A high frequency capsule is utilized to assess the CTDDS's relative bioavailability. Benefits of relative bioavailability and drug release at multiple GIT locations The factors for absorption were assessed and compared.

CURRENT AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

For colonic delivery, a number of modified release solid formulation technologies are currently available. These technologies are GI-dependent. enterobacteria, transit times, pH, and luminal pressure for delivery that is site-specific. any one of these technologies is a distinct system in Despite several flaws in terms of design, which frequently linked to site specificity, Cost, toxicity, and scale ability up/manufacturing. Colonic distribution appears to be most effective with microbially controlled systems based on natural polymers. especially with regard to site-specificity and safety. In this respect, formulas that use a technique for coating films using a mix of a film-forming polysaccharide and an appropriate chemical Polymer is a key technological advancement. Additional information about this area need ways to enhance coprocessing of a polymeric mixture polysaccharide(s) and a substance that forms films while preserving the tendency of the due to microbial deterioration in the makeup colon

CONCLUSION

The oral route stands as the foremost preference for drug administration, particularly when aiming for systemic effects. However, the oral route proves inadequate for delivering intended to treat lower gastrointestinal diseases as they often encounter premature release within the upper gastrointestinal tract, there has been a comprehensive and extensive analysis of colon-specific drug delivery system over the past two decades. These specialized are designed to precisely target drugs to specific sites within the colon, there by augmenting the therapeutic impact of the absorbed in contemporary medical practice, drugs are increasingly directed towards the colon via the rectal route in the recent years, has gained prominence as a means to precisely target drug delivery to colon enabling the potential for both localized and systemic drug effects in local drug delivery system we can treat bowel disease such as ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease, Amoebiasis, colonic cancer. To achieve effective colon-targeted drug delivery, it is necessary to safeguard the drug from degradation, premature release, and absorption in the upper gastrointestinal tract and ensure precise control of its release while protecting it from degradation in the colon. The colon-targeted drug delivery system can elicit both localized effects within the colon and systemic effects. The primary advantages of such a system include a prolonged transit time, maintenance of a near-neutral pH, reduced enzymatic activity, and improved responsiveness to absorption enhancers. The main objective of colon-targeted drug delivery systems is to safeguard the drug formulation as it traverses through the stomach and small intestine. Developing effective formulations for colon targeting presents significant challenges due to the necessity for precise drug release exclusively within the colon. Multiple methods are employed to formulate these colon-targeted drug delivery systems. Novel strategies, such as pressure-controlled drug delivery systems, pulsincap systems, port systems, and colon-targeted delivery systems, employ a combination of polysaccharides and synthetic polymers for drug delivery to the colon. These approaches offer a secure, efficient, and cost-effective means of drug delivery, minimizing fluctuations at the intended site of action.

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